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MEDICAL-BIOLOGICAL AND ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE MEASUREMENT OF TOBACCO SMOKE COMPONENTS IN THEIR IDENTIFICATION

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Abstract. This work makes it possible to assess the degree of purity of the atmosphere around us in open and practically closed air spaces, to determine the degree of risk to which not only an active, but also a passive smoker is exposed. The importance of such studies is increasing, because the category of passive smokers always includes children, youth and teenage populations. The paper shows several important results in biology, medicine and ecology, as well as the presence in the human body of toxic components and derivatives of tobacco smoke directly affects the life and health of active and passive smokers. The article offers guidelines for researchers and professionals working in the field of quantitative and qualitative measurement of components and derivatives of tobacco smoke.

Keywords: tobacco smoke, toxicity, substances, identification, quantitative analysis, qualitative analysis.

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აბსტრაქტი. ეს ნამუშევარი შესაძლებელს ხდის შეფასდეს ჩვენს ირგვლივ ატმოსფეროს სისუფთავის ხარისხი ღია და პრაქტიკულად დახურულ საჰაერო სივრცეებში, დადგინდეს რისკის ხარისხი, რომელსაც ექვემდებარება არა მხოლოდ აქტიური, არამედ პასიური მწველიც. ასეთი კვლევების მნიშვნელობა იზრდება, რადგან პასიურ მწველთა კატეგორიაში ყოველთვის შედის ბავშვები, ახალგაზრდები და მოზარდები. ნაშრომში ნაჩვენებია რამდენიმე მნიშვნელოვანი შედეგი ბიოლოგიაში, მედიცინასა და ეკოლოგიაში, ასევე ადამიანის ორგანიზმში თამბაქოს კვამლის ტოქსიკური კომპონენტებისა და წარმოებულების არსებობა პირდაპირ გავლენას ახდენს აქტიური და პასიურ მწველთა სიცოცხლესა და ჯანმრთელობაზე. სტატიაში მოცემულია სახელმძღვანელო მითითებები მკვლევარებისთვის და პროფესიონალებისთვის, რომლებიც მუშაობენ თამბაქოს კვამლის კომპონენტებისა და წარმოებულების რაოდენობრივი და ხარისხობრივი გაზომვის სფეროში.

Aim and objectives. In modern conditions, bioecological and biomedical monitoring, identification of atmospheric air pollutants, their quantitative and qualitative classification, and determination of the toxicity spectrum for humans and warm-blooded animals are of great importance. Therefore, the main objective of the article is to offer, based on our research, the best methods for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of substances in cigarette smoke and the

resulting derivatives to all interested parties and those who work on the identification of substances in tobacco smoke.

Actuality. The range of scientific research related to the problems of tobacco smoke is unusually wide. These studies are always based on medical and social norms. In practical terms, it is especially important to study the toxic effect of individual components of tobacco smoke (or their combination) on the body, organs and organ systems of not only active, but also passive smokers, as well as on metabolic changes that are pathognomic for each toxic component of tobacco smoke. According to modern concepts, the carcinogenicity of tobacco smoke is much higher than the combustion product of a tobacco product inhaled through a cigarette filter. Thus, a passive smoker is at greater risk than an active smoker [1; 2; 3].

Recently, more and more work has been published on the medical and biological aspects of the effects of tobacco smoke on the body of a passive smoker. The integrity and nature of the development of scientific research in this area are provided by the methodology of the approach based on an adequate concept of the nature of the phenomenon under study, which in general includes various kinds of environmental pollution problems with tobacco smoke products. Currently, the biomedical issues of the impact of cigarette smoke on the health of an active smoker are quite well studied. However, the effects of tobacco smoke on non-smokers (passive smokers) have not been sufficiently studied.

At such moments, the measurement of the dynamics of changes in the concentration and quality of toxic substances in time and space is of particular importance.

Introduction. Tobacco smoke in its structure is an aerosol containing vapor and microparticles. Although nicotine is most often measured as the main component in the determination of the structure of the vapor phase of tobacco smoke, it is not an ideal marker, due to the unpredictable rate and not fully understood degradation pathways (photochemical processes in the surrounding atmosphere), as well as high adsorption properties [1; 4; 5; 6].

The problem of combating the causes of environmental pollution is the most important task of modern mankind. The fulfillment of this problem depends on preventive measures, which are based on public-medical and socio-medical mechanisms. These mechanisms include individual elements of analytical chemistry. The relevance of toxicological studies of the air environment is increasing dramatically. Regular measurements of toxic substances in the surrounding atmosphere show that their biological exposures do not always correlate with the results of air analysis. The correlation changes are due to the following reasons: the penetration of toxic substances into the body is possible in other ways than the respiratory organs; non-professional exposure (passive smoker), and genetically determined physiological factors. Despite the obviousness of these facts, the study of all toxic substances that pollute our atmosphere is still highly relevant. In this aspect, the most dangerous is their combination and duration of action [3; 12; 13].

There is an understanding of real and potential environmental pollutants. The components of cigarette smoke are commonly referred to as potential pollutants. The components of tobacco smoke are dangerous not only due to their general toxic effect, but also because they cause teratogenic, mutagenic, gonadotropic, carcinogenic and many other effects [7; 8; 14].

Therefore, a comprehensive study of the prevalence of each component of tobacco smoke in the atmosphere, the dependence of their concentrations on temperature, humidity, lighting and distance from the source of pollution (active smoker), acquires practical significance and perspective in medical and eco-biological aspects [9; 10; 13; 16].

Materials and methods. The method of qualitative and quantitative identification of tobacco smoke components is quite complicated, because sampling and determination of concentrations of suspended particles depends mainly on the nature and conditions of ventilation of closed and open spaces.

Air sampling to determine the components of tobacco smoke is most often carried out by the aspiration method, based on pulling a specific volume of air through the absorption system [1; 11].

The degree of capture in modern absorbers reaches 90-99%, with a determination error not exceeding 3.0%. Liquid absorbers are most commonly used.

Sanitary and hygienic assessment of pollution of the surrounding air, as well as the air of residential and public buildings, is carried out on the basis of a comparison of the compliance of the actual level of the content of substances with the average daily MPC in the atmospheric air. Maximum Permissible Levels (MACs) have been developed and Approximate Safe Exposure Levels (SHLI) have been approved for many chemical compounds polluting the atmospheric air: substances used in the national economy, used in industry, etc. [18].

From the point of view of Sanitary and hygienic control, at present, there are officially only a small number of standardized substances for which metrologically certified control methods and permissible levels are defined and approved.

Most of the officially accepted methods used in analytical control are based on the principle of targeted analysis, which is often limited by the number of indicators.

Such an approach is not capable of fully controlling the content of unknown and non-standardized substances in the air and assessing their impact on public health. This is due to the fact that in conditions of multicomponent environmental pollution (the number of toxic components is constantly increasing), sanitary and hygienic control of the quality of atmospheric air, as well as indoor and outdoor air (residential environment) for the existing components of toxic hazard is insufficient, since each the object under study in most cases contains specific, previously undetermined substances [1; 18].

Under the influence of environmental factors, the components of tobacco smoke are often transformed, forming more toxic and dangerous substances compared to the original ones. In this regard, it becomes necessary to use multicomponent analytical methods for monitoring environmental objects using separate variants of chromatographic methods of analysis that can qualitatively and quantitatively identify a wide range of unknown pollutants in the atmosphere and give them a metrological assessment.

This type of multicomponent analytical approach, along with the control of standardized and unknown non-standardized substances, the effect of which on a living organism has not been finally determined until recently, and therefore in most cases remained uncontrolled, is extremely informative when searching for a source of air pollution in open and closed rooms according to hygienically significant indicators and values of environmental and hygienic standards.

Currently, there is no consensus on the "quantitative threshold" at which a clear separation of "minor" and "trace" components representing the "risk factor" is possible. Air (in the sense of the matrix) is considered a "simple system" that contains a colossal amount of basic, minor and trace components, each of which can be of tremendous (sometimes decisive) importance in terms of the nature of the local microclimate during long-term or short-term exposure to even low concentrations. However, in comparison with the analysis of "minor components" of organic compounds, the qualitative and quantitative identification of their "trace" values based on the

development of especially sensitive analytical methods (within ppm and pbm according to the CN system) can be considered quite acceptable [1; 5; 18; 19; 20; 21].

The method of gas-liquid chromatography makes it possible to qualitatively separate and quantitatively analyze volatile compounds with high accuracy on gamma quantities of mixtures that cannot be determined by any other known physicochemical methods [1; 17].

Recently, more and more work has been published on the medical and biological aspects of the effects of tobacco smoke on the body of a passive smoker. The integrity and nature of the development of scientific research in this area are provided by the methodology based on an adequate concept of the nature of the phenomenon under study, which in general includes various kinds of environmental pollution problems with tobacco smoke products. Currently, the bio-medical issues of the impact of cigarette smoke on the health of an active smoker are quite well studied. However, the effects of tobacco smoke on non-smokers (passive smokers) have not been sufficiently studied. We are talking about the toxic effect of individual components of tobacco smoke (nicotine, tar, high molecular weight compounds, etc.) located at cut distances. In different concentrations and different durations from an active and passive smoker. The physicochemical and bio-ecological aspects of this process are almost not studied. The ability of individual components of tobacco smoke to be spread by air flows through the microsphere surrounding a person has not been determined. The complexity of this issue is associated with many issues, of which the main ones are:

- physical and chemical parameters of each component of tobacco smoke, since high-temperature smoking products can exhibit a synergistic effect with other mutagens;
- the nature of the environment (parameters of the atmospheric environment);
- the intensity of the source of pollution, and the activity of the smoker.

It is believed that the first and last puffs differ from each other in terms of the content of individual components of tobacco smoke. For example, the first puff contains no more than 0.9 ng CO and no more than 3.6 ng CO₂. While, in the subsequent puff, these components increase to 1.9 ng (CO) and 5.6 ng (CO₂).

Depending on the distance from the source of pollution and the duration of inhalation of tobacco smoke, a passive smoker is exposed to chronic intoxication of varying degrees and of a different nature. The severity of intoxication also depends on the ability of each toxic agent to accumulate in the body of a passive smoker and, thereby, cause life-threatening irreversible changes in tissues, organs and biological systems.

At present, it is practically unknown how the concentration of individual components of tobacco smoke changes at different distances from a burning cigarette. The role of the main environmental parameters (air temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, degree of illumination, etc.) on the nature of the movement and the migration of each component of the smoke during smoking has not been determined. There are almost no studies according to which one can get a concrete idea of how the concentration of each component of tobacco smoke changes at different distances from a burning cigarette at low (almost minus) and high (maximum comfortable for a person) air temperature.

This type of work makes it possible to assess the degree of purity of the atmosphere around us in open and practically closed air spaces, to determine the degree of risk to which a passive smoker is exposed. The importance of such studies is increasing, because passive smokers always include children, youth and adolescent populations.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of the components of tobacco smoke is given by adsorption gas-liquid chromatography on a PPF-Milliporwaters gas chromatograph (USA). A

quartz capillary column 120.0 meters long and 0.35 mm in diameter was used. The walls of the capillary are coated with the stationary liquid phase OV-101. Coating thickness 5.0 microns. Carrier gas consumption (helium) - 3.0 ml/min. Retention value 20,800 theoretical plates (for benzene). The principle of temperature programming is used. After the introduction of the sample within 8.0 minutes was maintained isothermal mode (20°C). Next came programming in increments of 2.0 g/min up to a maximum temperature of 200.0 °C, and then the isothermal mode was maintained. Evaporator temperature 240.0°C, detector temperature 260°C. Flame ionization detector. Discharge to atmosphere up to 80.0%. The so-called "support" method was used, which is based on the supply of gas to the detector through a specialized fitting (bypass line) in a volume of 20.0 ml/min. Dosing was done with a Hamilton-N6 microsyringe. The area of each chromatographic peak was calculated using the corrected retention time on a Model 730 integrator, Data-Module (Waters) Program N4. The spread of concentrations determined in cigarette smoke of substances was covered by a combination of several independent chromatographic channels (pair inclusion), which made it possible to carry out a fairly reliable assessment (scatter no more than 2.0%) both in the upper and lower (trace volumes) concentrations. In all cases, the probability of sorption of substances in gas communications (mirror values of the electrical response) was taken into account.

Results and discussion. Qualitative and quantitative analysis of nicotine, benzene, propylbenzene, toluene, xylene, phenol, styrene, isoprene, formic and acetic acids in tobacco smoke was carried out in the most securely closed room with a volume of 36.0 m³.

Cigarettes with the following technological parameters were used: cigarette length 70.0 ± 0.5 mm; cigarette tape width 28.0 ± 2.0 mm; fiber width 0.7 mm with tolerances, respectively, not higher than 20.0%. In the proposed work, we do not provide brands and technologies for the production of tobacco products, as well as the botanical origin and grade of raw materials. In a smoking machine, as a standard, products were smoked that were strictly uniform in terms of the place of manufacture (factory, production line, machine tools, etc.) and the nature of storage. According to standard requirements, the characteristics of tissue paper, sizing, filters, dyes, clichés were the same as possible.

The distal part of the tobacco product was separated with a razor, weighed (2.0 g) and, together with the rim paper, was placed in the pyrolyzer drum. The hole was hermetically sealed. As soon as the temperature of the drum of the smoking machine reached 600° C, the hole opened on its own and the tobacco smoke entered the atmosphere of the room.

The studies were carried out at three different room temperatures:

- cold air, but not frost (3.0 - 5.0°C),
- comfortable ambient temperature (18-20°C),
- maximum allowable indoor temperature (38-40°C).

The analysis of cigarette smoke was carried out at distances of one, two, three, four, five, six, seven, eight and nine meters from the smoking machine in the following sequence: after 10.0 minutes; 20.0 minutes; 50.0 minutes; 100.0 minutes and 150.0 minutes after the start of the experiment (opening the pyrolyzer lid). The experiments were carried out three times for each zone and were processed accordingly. In order to eliminate residual concentrations of cigarette smoke products, an interval of 15 days was carried out between each experiment. At the same time, before the start of each experiment, a chromatographic analysis of air was carried out to exclude background pollution.

The method of "point selection" was used, which makes it possible to study the composition of the air environment by chromatography methods at specific distances from the smoking

machine at a fixed time (according to a given program). The sample probe (4 at each point) was placed in such a way as to completely exclude the mutual overlap of air samples. The reverse exhaust was extinguished by a special filter.

The identification of organic substances in tobacco smoke is of great importance in medicine, biology and ecology. Their presence directly affects the lives and health of smokers and non-smokers. The increased interest on the part of the general public in these problems of environmental protection, and the tasks of clinical chemistry and medicine is quite understandable.

The influence of the matrix on the yield of analytes is very high. For example: during the determination of nicotine and cotinine in tissues (hairline) and biological fluids (saliva) at concentrations from 2 to 3 ng/mg, the yield of these components differed by 80 and 89%, respectively, in the air - slightly less.

Determination of organic matter introduced by man is usually associated with environmental issues. This problem in almost all cases is due to the activity of the person himself. Any changes are controlled by the public (also legal) introduction of relevant rules and regulations. However, they are based and controlled to a greater extent by subjective sensations, and not by objective data (the adoption of new norms, rules and restrictions).

A rapidly developing field of analysis of organic compounds is the study of their metabolism, in particular, the kinetics of metabolic transformations of combustion products of tobacco products during smoking (puff) by active smokers (thermal, photochemical processes). Public response to tobacco smoke toxicity problems, unfortunately, usually only emerges after persistently expressed general public anxiety.

Air pollution control is usually rated at the picogram level. Recommendations and research rules are especially needed when identifying highly toxic components of tobacco smoke.

The identification and evaluation of trace compounds of great medical interest also require consideration of the specific contribution of background contaminants in the course of the analytical response.

The generally accepted opinion regarding the level of concentration, which makes it possible to use the term "trace amounts", does not yet definitively exist.

It is generally accepted that if a component is contained in a substance (or mixture of substances) called a "matrix", not more than 0.1% quantitatively, the use of the term "trace values" is fully justified.

Trace is currently considered to be in the ppm range, but more often even lower in ppm, in the so-called matrix. Abbreviations and units of measurement express the quantitative system of internationally accepted units (SI). They make it possible to eliminate the sometimes-ambiguous quantification. For purely practical reasons, concentrations are often expressed in very arbitrary units, for example: a large number of tobacco smoke components are often estimated as their number (per cigarette).

In our studies, the matrix has an organic (hair, saliva, blood plasma, sweat) and inorganic nature (air, main and side cigarette smoke). The assessment of the significance of each matrix was carried out according to the chromatographic method.

Gas-liquid chromatography is a detail of minor and trace components, each of which can be of tremendous (sometimes decisive) importance in terms of the nature of the local microclimate during long-term or short-term exposure to even low concentrations. However, in comparison with the analysis of "minor components" of organic compounds, the qualitative and quantitative identification of their "trace" values based on the development of especially sensitive

analytical methods (within ppm and pbm according to the CN system) can be considered quite acceptable.

In order to optimize the analysis process: retention rate, selectivity, and number of theoretical plates, the following regulatory factors were applied: separation selectivity, which was determined by comparing the retention rate of two peaks (retention time and volume and separation modes), which were determined by the strength of the solvent (eluting power), the nature of the packing and the volume of the column.

It is known that the number of theoretical plates serves as a measure of the width of the peaks in a particular chromatographic system. It is proportional to the square of the ratio of retention volume to peak width. The resolution equation is as follows:

$$R_s = \underbrace{1/4\sqrt{N}}_{\text{Efficiency}} \times \underbrace{\frac{\alpha-1}{\alpha}}_{\text{Selectivity}} \times \underbrace{\frac{k}{1+k}}_{\text{Retention}}$$

where R_s is the resolution of the chromatographic column, K is the degree of retention, α is the selectivity or the ratio of the degrees of retention of the two peaks of interest to us, N is the number of theoretical plates.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of nicotine in the air includes the following steps: concentration from the air with a specially prepared adsorbent, extraction with diethyl ether, evaporation to organic oil, re-extraction with ethanol, gas chromatographic separation on a capillary column and quantitative determination.

The concentration of nicotine in the atmospheric air (mg/m^3) is calculated according to the formula:

$$C = \frac{m}{V_0}$$

M - mass of nicotine, according to the calibration characteristic

V_0 - the volume of air taken for analysis and reduced to normal conditions.

C - measurement results.

The confidence error of measurement should not exceed 23% at a confidence level of 0.95.

We consider it necessary to provide quality control indicators for the reproducibility of fixed retention times (\pm minutes) of our chromatographic analysis.

Conclusion. Thus, the identification of organic substances in tobacco smoke is of great importance in medicine, biology and ecology. Their presence directly affects the life and health of smokers and non-smokers.

Specific areas of qualitative analysis of toxic compounds are usually divided into two categories. The first category includes the determination of compounds directly introduced by the person himself, the second category - the definition of natural compounds. Each of these categories takes into account the principle of the origin of the test sample in its matrix, and relies mainly on existing legal acts.

In our studies, the matrix has an organic (hair, saliva, blood plasma, sweat) and inorganic nature (air, main and side cigarette smoke). The assessment of the significance of each matrix was carried out according to the chromatographic method.

Gas-liquid chromatography is a highly developed, extremely sensitive and long-used method of analytical chemistry. Approximately more than 50% of the work on the quantitative and qualitative analysis of trace levels of organic substances is based on the application of this methodological approach.

The method of gas-liquid chromatography makes it possible to qualitatively separate and quantitatively analyze volatile compounds with high accuracy on gamma quantities of mixtures that cannot be determined by any other known physicochemical methods.

The possibility of separation and qualitative and quantitative identification of all combustion products of tobacco products, the study of their carcinogenic, mutagenic and thermogenic activity, is extremely difficult, and in some cases practically unrealistic. This is due to both - their low concentration in the air and the methodological issues of separating and identifying multicomponent systems of different classes in minor terms.

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